

FAILURE MECHANISM OF TITANIUM-BASED CARBON-FIBRE/EPOXY LAMINATES UNDER TENSION

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ABSTRACT

Titanium-based carbon-fibre/epoxy laminates (TI-CF FMLs), are layered materials based on stacked arrangements of titanium alloy layers and carbon-fibre/epoxy laminated layers, having benefits over both constituent materials. In this study, the tensile properties of the TI-CF FMLs were investigated under quasi-static loading. A comprehensive experimental study was conducted for nine different types of the TI-CF FMLs (considering various metal sheet thicknesses, metal volume fractions and fibre orientations) as well as their associated constituent materials (i.e., Ti-6Al-4V and CF/E laminates). The stress-strain curves of the TI-CF FMLs, which characterized into three stages, were analyzed. Each stage of failure were explained in detail. In addition, the specific energy absorption of the TI-CF FMLs were evaluated in this study.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the recent types of the fibre metal laminates (FML), titanium-based carbon-fibre/epoxy laminates (TI-CF FMLs), are hybrid materials made of laminated carbon-fibre/epoxy (CF/E) interspersed with thin titanium layers as shown in Fig. 1 [1–5]. TI-CF FMLs have the ability to tailor material properties so that the attractive features of the aforementioned constituent materials can be used and their weakness can be overcome. The titanium layers provide improved durability, bearing and impact resistance whereas the CF/E laminates core offer higher stiffness- and strength-to-weight ratios as well as superior fracture and fatigue resistances [6–10].

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of TI-CF FML.

Prevailing research has been mainly focused on the fatigue properties of the TI-CF FML [11]. For example, Yao *et al.* [12] and Li *et al.* [13] indicate the fatigue properties of the TI-CF FML is superior than that of the monolithic titanium alloy. The enhanced fatigue resistance of the TI-CF FML was found due to the reduce crack growth rates as a result of the introduced fibre-bridging effect. Tensile behaviour of the TI-CF FML has attracted limited research. Bourlegat *et al.* [14] conducted quasi-static tensile tests on the TI-CF FML and found that the tensile properties of the TI-CF FML are superior compared with glass-fibre reinforced aluminium laminate (GLARE) and carbon-fibre reinforced aluminium laminate (CARALL). Cortes and Cantwell [15] demonstrated that the Young's modulus of the TI-CF FML could be predicted using the classical laminate theory and the other tensile properties could be obtained with the recommended failure criteria. Although these researches indicated that TI-CF FMLs offer excellent mechanical performance, limited number of tensile tests were performed. Given that the tensile behaviour of the TI-CF FMLs is influenced by the configuration scheme of their constituent materials, a comprehensive study is required considering various metal sheet thicknesses, metal volume fractions (*MVFs*) and fibre orientations. In addition, in order to evaluate the energy absorption efficiency of the TI-CF FMLs, specific energy absorption (*SEA*) which is an important indicator need to be calculated and analyzed [16].

In this paper, we experimentally evaluate the tensile behaviour of the TI-CF FMLs. The design of the TI-CF FMLs and experimental procedure are described in Section 2. Experimental tensile stress-strain curves are presented in Section 3. Failure mechanisms are also discussed within the same section. In addition, the specific energy absorption of the TI-CF FMLs is discussed in Section 4.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

The TI-CF FMLs investigated in this research consist of 360 g/m² uni-directional carbon-fibre/epoxy prepreg (UD CF/E prepreg) having a fibre mass fraction of 58% and a thickness of 0.45 mm, and grade 5 α - β Ti-6Al-4V titanium alloy with various thicknesses: 0.3 mm, 0.4 mm, 0.5 mm, and 0.6 mm. The number of the metal layers per specimen equals to 2. The configuration notation used here is TI-CF FML (t_{me}) – n_{fi} ($\theta_1/\theta_2/\dots$) which represents t_{me} mm thickness of each Ti-6Al-4V, and n_{fi} plies of the UD CF/E prepregs with specified fibre lay-up orientation (i.e. $\theta_1/\theta_2/\dots$). An example of the lay-up scheme of TI-CF FMLs (0.4) – 4 (0°-45°/+45°/90°) is depicted in Fig. 2. In order to conduct a comprehensive study, nine representative TI-CF FMLs have been designed considering various metal sheet thicknesses, metal volume fractions and fibre orientations as listed in Table 1. The specimens were fabricated using vacuum bagging technique in an autoclave.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of TI-CF FML (0.4) – 4 (0°-45°/+45°/90°).

TI-CF FML	Metal layer	Fibre layer	
Notation	Thickness of each metal layers	Number of UD CF/E prepreg plies	UD CF/E prepreg lay-up orientation
$(t_{me}) - n_{fi} (\theta_1/\theta_2/\dots)$	t_{me} (mm)	n_{fi}	$(\theta_1/\theta_2/\dots)$
(0.4) – 2 (0°/0°)	0.4	2	(0°/0°)
(0.4) – 2 (0°/90°)	0.4	2	(0°/90°)
(0.4) – 3 (0°/90°/0°)	0.4	3	(0°/90°/0°)
(0.4) – 3 (90°/0°/90°)	0.4	3	(90°/0°/90°)
(0.4) – 4 (0°/90°/90°/0°)	0.4	4	(0°/90°/90°/0°)
(0.4) – 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	0.4	4	(0°/-45°/+45°/90°)
(0.3) – 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	0.3	4	(0°/-45°/+45°/90°)
(0.5) – 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	0.5	4	(0°/-45°/+45°/90°)
(0.6) – 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	0.6	4	(0°/-45°/+45°/90°)

Table 1: Investigated types of TI-CF FMLs.

2.2 Specimens

According to ASTM D3039 [17], all the specimens were water-jet cut to standard size 25 mm × 250 mm (width w × length l). The thicknesses (t) and masses (m) of the specimens were measured by Hilka digital calliper and A&D electronic balance scale (EP-12KA model) respectively. Detailed specimen specifications are recorded in Appendix Table A1. The typical density ($\rho = \frac{m}{t \times w \times l}$) and MVF (which is defined as the thickness ratio of all the metal layers to the overall thickness of the TI-CF FML) [18–20] can be calculated accordingly with the measured thickness and mass values as shown in Table 2.

Notation	ρ (kg/m ³)	MVF (%)
(0.4) – 2 (0°/0°)	3533.0	50.0
(0.4) – 2 (0°/90°)	3533.0	50.0
(0.4) – 3 (0°/90°/0°)	3139.4	40.4
(0.4) – 3 (90°/0°/90°)	3139.4	40.4
(0.4) – 4 (0°/90°/90°/0°)	2867.1	33.9
(0.4) – 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	2867.1	33.9
(0.3) – 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	2700.7	27.8
(0.5) – 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	3005.0	39.1
(0.6) – 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	3136.2	43.5

Table 2: Summary of physical properties of TI-CF FMLs.

2.3 Tensile tests

Figure 3: The MTS and experimental set-up.

The quasi-static tensile test was performed on an MTS universal testing machine, as shown in Fig. 3. The MTS machine is equipped with MTS 793 software and integrated data acquisition system (i.e., ± 250 kN load cell). Tensile strain was measured by using MTS laser extensometer (model No. LX500). Canon EOS 650D camera and Canon EOS 6D camera were employed for taking photographs and videos of the front- and side-view of the specimen during the tests respectively in order to analyse the failure mechanism. The specimens were fully clamped by means of two sets of jaws with 150 mm gauge length. According to ASTM D3039, all tensile tests were performed at quasi-static crosshead loading speed of 2 mm/min. Five repeated tests were conducted for per test condition, leading to a total of over 100 tests.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Stress-strain curves of the constituent materials

The tensile stress-strain curves of the constituent materials are depicted in Fig. 4. Mean values of the tested mechanical properties of the CF/E laminates and Ti-6Al-4V (including Young's modulus (E), yield/ultimate stresses (σ_y/σ_u), and yield/ultimate/failure strains ($\varepsilon_y/\varepsilon_u/\varepsilon_f$) are summarized in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively. Values inside bracket are the standard deviation.

It can be seen from the stress-strain curve, the CF/E laminates fail in a brittle manner at their maximum failure strain in the range of 1.36% – 1.45%. The laminate designed with more 0° fibres leads to much higher values of elastic Young's modulus and tensile failure strength compared with those aligned with the angles other than 0°. This is because carbon-fibre with 90° or 45° alignment has no or little contribution to the overall tensile strength of the CF/E laminate material. The Ti-6Al-4V fails in a ductile manner and its strain hardening effect is negligible.

Figure 4: Stress-strain curves of the CF/E laminates and Ti-6Al-4V.

Notation	E (GPa)	σ_f (MPa)	ε_f (%)
CF/E 2 (0°/0°)	123.2 (5.4)	1743.0 (57.5)	1.36 (0.09)
CF/E 2 (90°/90°)	7.9 (0.7)	20.0 (2.5)	0.24 (0.04)
CF/E 2 (0°/90°)	64.0 (1.2)	886.7 (44.0)	1.42 (0.11)
CF/E 2 (-45°/+45°)	14.5 (1.0)	59.8 (2.1)	0.88 (0.17)
CF/E 3 (0°/90°/0°)	77.2 (1.1)	1088.1 (57.5)	1.42 (0.09)
CF/E 3 (90°/0°/90°)	43.0 (1.1)	618.9 (33.5)	1.45 (0.04)
CF/E 4 (0°/90°/90°/0°)	63.6 (1.4)	914.9 (80.8)	1.45 (0.08)
CF/E 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	39.3 (1.0)	547.4 (29.7)	1.43 (0.04)

Table 3: Summary of tensile properties of CF/E laminates.

Notation	E (GPa)	σ_y (MPa)	ε_y (%)	σ_u (MPa)	ε_u (%)	ε_f (%)
Ti-6Al-4V	113.5 (3.5)	931.1 (15.7)	0.82 (0.02)	1034.0 (9.9)	4.01 (0.65)	5.37 (0.71)

Table 4: Summary of tensile properties of Ti-6Al-4V.

3.2 Stress-strain curves of the TI-CF FMLs

The tensile behaviour and the failure mechanisms of the nine types of TI-CF FMLs are investigated in this sub-section. The stress-strain curves as well as photographs of the specimens after the tensile tests are presented in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 respectively. The mechanical properties of the TI-CF FMLs are summarized in Table 5.

Figure 5: The stress-strain curves of the TI-CF FMLs.

Figure 6: Specimens after tensile tests.

Notation	E (GPa)	σ_f (MPa)	ϵ_f (%)
TI-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (0°/0°)	110.2 (0.9)	1359.1 (31.3)	1.49 (0.07)
TI-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (90°/90°)	68.4 (2.6)	537.6 (5.3)	1.09 (0.04)
TI-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (0°/90°)	91.0 (2.8)	970.2 (30.1)	1.47 (0.10)
TI-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (-45°/+45°)	65.5 (4.0)	506.1 (8.5)	0.80 (0.05)
TI-CF FML (0.4) - 3 (0°/90°/0°)	95.6 (4.6)	1137.1 (65.6)	1.47 (0.12)
TI-CF FML (0.4) - 3 (90°/0°/90°)	79.5 (2.1)	779.9 (18.9)	1.37 (0.08)
TI-CF FML (0.4) - 4 (0°/90°/90°/0°)	84.2 (4.7)	933.2 (40.7)	1.41 (0.13)
TI-CF FML (0.4) - 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	66.1 (2.0)	756.4 (21.3)	1.59 (0.10)
TI-CF FML (0.3) - 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	65.3 (4.6)	727.6 (23.7)	1.51 (0.06)
TI-CF FML (0.5) - 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	68.1 (5.1)	763.1 (44.8)	1.49 (0.20)
TI-CF FML (0.6) - 4 (0°/-45°/+45°/90°)	73.8 (3.9)	804.3 (31.6)	1.53 (0.17)

Table 5: Summary of tensile properties of TI-CF FMLs.

The stress-strain curves of the TI-CF FMLs can be considered as three stages: Stage I, Stage II and Stage III, as marked in Fig. 5. Taking TI-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (0°/0°) as an example, its stress-strain curve features the first two stages. Stage I starts with zero tensile stress and strain and then stress increases linearly with strain. Stage I terminates when the yielding strain of the metal layer is reached, which is approximately 0.82% as in Table 4 for the Ti-6Al-4V. In this stage, both the fibre and metal layers behave elastically. In Stage II, the fibre layers still deform elastically, and the metal layers deform, however, plastically. This is also the reason for the change in the slope of the stress-strain curves from Stage I to Stage II. Unlike Stage I, the termination of Stage II is controlled by the maximum failure strain of the fibre layers (refer to Table 3). It is interesting to note that, once the 0° fibre layers break, the deformation of the entire FML specimen takes place only in the metal layers, and more importantly, the deformation is localized around the fibre breaking point (due to the lack of fibre-bridging effect [21]). This phenomenon can be confirmed by the strain field of the specimen just before failure, which captured by using a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique, VIC-2D Correlated Solutions, as depicted in Fig. 7. The highest strain value measured, 5.69%, is approximately the same as the failure strain of the metal layer (5.37% as recorded in Table 4).

Figure 7: Strain field for the TI-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (0°/0°) just before failure.

The stress-strain curves of the TI-CF FML (0.4) - 3 (0°/90°/0°) and (0.4) - 3 (0°/90°/90°/0°) follow exactly the same pattern. However, due to the introduced 90° fibre(s), inter-delamination (which refer to shear failure between the UD CF/E prepreg plies or the fibre layer with its adjacent metal layer) was observed as a result of inner-delamination (failure is along the fibre-matrix interface) of the 90° fibre, see photographs in Fig. 6.

Stage I and Stage II of the TI-CF FML (0.4) - 3 (90°/0°/90°) are the same as the aforementioned two stages. The additional Stage III starts when the fibre layer breaks and terminates when the metal skins on both sides of the TI-CF FML fail. It is worth mentioning that the metal layers tend to delaminate and

behave independently due to the adjacent 90° fibre. This also explains the fact that in Stage III, the magnitude of the stress when both metal layers deforming plastically is twice as much as that when one side of the metal layer deforms plastically (i.e. point A) while the other side of metal layer has experienced ductile failure (i.e. point B) as marked in Fig. 5.

For the TI-CF FML (0.4) - 2 ($0^\circ/90^\circ$), when Stage II terminates, the metal layer next to the 0° fibre layer fails simultaneously with the fibre layer at strains in the range of 1.27 – 1.53% as a result of the lack of fibre-bridging effect around the fibre breaking point. The metal layer bonded with the 90° fibre layer behaves independently as described in Stage III until the failure point is reached.

The stress-strain curves for the aforementioned stages are also applicable to TI-CF FMLs of CF/E 4 ($0^\circ/45^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ$) laminated cores. Importantly, the metal layer (next to the 90° fibre layer) either fails independently in a ductile manner after delamination as described in Stage III, or experiences localised failure at the end of Stage II as a result of inadequate delamination, which depends on the value of metal volume fraction, MVF . As recorded, the higher the value of MVF , the metal layer adjacent to the 90° fibre layer tends to delaminate and fails independently, e.g., TI-CF FML (0.6) - 4 ($0^\circ/45^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ$), $MVF = 43.5\%$ (Table 2). On the other hand, for the lower value of MVF , the failure of that metal layer is localised due to the existence of the fibre-bridging effect as a result of inadequate delamination, e.g., TI-CF FML (0.3) - 4 ($0^\circ/45^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ$), $MVF = 27.8\%$ (Table 2). For the TI-CF FML (0.4) - 4 ($0^\circ/45^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ$) in which its MVF is calculated as 33.9% (Table 2), the aforementioned failure modes occur approximately to the same degree as one or the other for that metal layer. The deformation mechanism is not clear and further investigation is required.

In summary, the three-stage tensile behaviour of TI-CF FMLs is depicted in Fig. 8. The failure points of the TI-CF FMLs have been defined as the termination point of the Stage II (that is controlled by the maximum failure strain of the fibre layers, ϵ_f^{fi}), not the Stage III (that is dictated by the failure strain of the metal layer, ϵ_f^{me}) as the third stage does not effectively contribute much for their engineering applications. In other words, the failure is dominated by the CF/E laminates and their failure strain (with a mean value of 1.48%) is also marginally greater or equal to that of the corresponding CF/E laminates. Compared with its dominated constituent materials, the slightly increased failure strain of the TI-CF FML is attributed to the fibre-bridging effect.

Figure 8: Schematics of the three-stage tensile behaviour of TI-CF FMLs (superscripts ‘ FML ’, ‘ me ’ and ‘ fi ’ symbolize the values of the strain properties associated with TI-CF FML, metal layer and fibre layer).

4 SPECIFIC ENERGY ABSORPTION

The specific energy absorption (SEA) as defined in equation (1) is an important indicator which reflects the energy absorption efficiency of the material [16]. Clearly, higher value of SEA indicates

higher efficiency of material usage for energy absorption. Given that the failure of the TI-CF FMLs is defined as the termination of Stage II, the amount of specific energy absorbed when the material is considered as non-failure, that is SEA_{II} , can be calculated by integrating the stress with respect to the strain (up to the failure strain of the fibre layer) divided by material density as shown in equation (2). The SEA for the entire three stages, denoted as SEA_{III} , can be evaluated by using equation (3) which gives the overall energy absorption ability of the material when subjected to tension. The SEA_{II} and SEA_{III} of the TI-CF FMLs as well as their associated constituent materials are shown in Fig. 9.

$$SEA = \frac{\int \sigma d\varepsilon}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

$$SEA_{II} = \frac{\int_0^{\varepsilon_f^{fi}} \sigma d\varepsilon}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

$$SEA_{III} = \frac{\int_0^{\varepsilon_f^{me}} \sigma d\varepsilon}{\rho} \quad (3)$$

Figure 9: SEA_{II} and SEA_{III} of Ti-6Al-4V, CF/E laminates and TI-CF FMLs.

In Fig. 9, once the Stage II terminates, in other words, the terminating strain value ($\epsilon_f^{f_i}$) is reached, the CF/E laminates with higher strength, but lightweight, offer a superior SEA_{II} response to that exhibited by the Ti-6Al-4V (which features relatively lower strength and higher density). The SEA_{II} for each type of the TI-CF FML lies between that of the constituent materials of CF/E laminate and Ti-6Al-4V. The energy absorption capacity of the TI-CF FML before Stage II is influenced by the CF/E laminates, that is the higher the SEA_{II} of the CF/E laminate result in increased SEA_{II} of the TI-CF FML provided that the metal layers are identical for all types of TI-CF FMLs.

It is note that, the SEA_{III} of the Ti-6Al-4V is significantly increased due to its plastic deformation whereas that calculated for CF/E laminates is equivalent to their evaluated SEA_{II} as the stress-strain curves of the CF/E laminates do not featuring Stage III. The SEA_{III} exhibited by the TI-CF FMLs either inferior to, or, lies between that of their constituent materials depending on the delamination degree. If no or less delamination occurs (e.g. TI-CF FML (0.4) – 2 (0 %)), energy absorption capacity of the laminate is lower compared with the associated CF/E 2 (0 % 0 %) and Ti-6Al-4V. However, more energy will be absorbed as a result of delamination (e.g. TI-CF FML (0.4) – 3 (90 % 90 %)), which leads to the increased SEA of the TI-CF FML from Stage II to Stage III. In addition, it is worth mentioning that with increase in the MVF (e.g. TI-CF FMLs with CF/E 4 (0 %-45 %+45 %90 %) laminated core), SEA_{III} is gradually enhanced.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The tensile properties of the TI-CF FMLs as well as their associated constituent materials have been investigated experimentally. The stress-strain curves for the TI-CF FMLs have displayed three stages: Stage I features the elastically behaved metal and fibre layers. Stage II represents the elastically deformed fibre layers with, however, plastically deformed metal layers. Stage III stands for the independently behaved metal layers when full delamination has occurred at the termination of Stage II.

The specimen failure mechanisms involving inner- and inter-delamination, fibre fracture as well as metal yielding have also been captured and analysed in this study. Given that the failure point is defined as the termination of Stage II, the failure of the TI-CF FMLs is dominated by the CF/E laminate cores (fibre layer).

It has been shown that the metal layer next to the 0 °fibre layer fails simultaneously when the adjacent fibre breaks, and the failure is localized around the fibre breaking point due to the lack of fibre-bridging effect. The metal layer bonded with the 90 °fibre layer fails independently in a ductile manner after delamination, except for TI-CF FMLs with CF/E 4 (0 %-45 %+45 %90 %) laminated core, where the failure type on that metal layer alters with lower value of MVF .

The SEA of the TI-CF FMLs, CF/E laminates and Ti-6Al-4V has been evaluated and analyzed for Stage I and Stage II (SEA_{II}) as well as the entire three stages (SEA_{III}). Results mainly revealed the fact that the SEA_{II} of the TI-CF FML is influenced by the CF/E laminate whereas the SEA_{III} of the TI-CF FML is affected by the material delamination degree.

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APPENDIX

Notation		t (mm)	$t \times w$ (mm ²)	m (g)
Constituent Materials	Ti-6Al-4V	1.50	37.5	44.9
	CF/E 2 (0 ° 0 °)	0.76	19.0	6.7
	CF/E 2 (90 ° 90 °)	0.76	19.0	6.7
	CF/E 2 (0 ° 90 °)	0.76	19.0	6.7
	CF/E 2 (-45 ° +45 °)	0.76	19.0	6.7
	CF/E 3 (0 ° 90 ° 0 °)	1.14	28.5	10.0
	CF/E 3 (90 ° 0 ° 90 °)	1.14	28.5	10.0
	CF/E 4 (0 ° 90 ° 90 ° 0 °)	1.52	38.0	13.4
	CF/E 4 (0 ° -45 ° +45 ° 90 °)	1.52	38.0	13.4
FML	Ti-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (0 ° 0 °)	1.60	40.0	35.3
	Ti-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (90 ° 90 °)	1.60	40.0	35.3
	Ti-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (0 ° 90 °)	1.60	40.0	35.3
	Ti-CF FML (0.4) - 2 (-45 ° +45 °)	1.60	40.0	35.3
	Ti-CF FML (0.4) - 3 (0 ° 90 ° 0 °)	1.98	49.5	38.9
	Ti-CF FML (0.4) - 3 (90 ° 0 ° 90 °)	1.98	49.5	38.9
	Ti-CF FML (0.4) - 4 (0 ° 90 ° 90 ° 0 °)	2.36	59.0	42.3
	Ti-CF FML (0.4) - 4 (0 ° -45 ° +45 ° 90 °)	2.36	59.0	42.3
	Ti-CF FML (0.3) - 4 (0 ° -45 ° +45 ° 90 °)	2.16	64.0	36.5
	Ti-CF FML (0.5) - 4 (0 ° -45 ° +45 ° 90 °)	2.56	69.0	48.1
	Ti-CF FML (0.6) - 4 (0 ° -45 ° +45 ° 90 °)	2.76	74.0	54.1

Table A1: Specifications of the specimen.

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